

A Study on Socio-economic Condition of Backward Class Community and its Development through Various Government Schemes in Maharashtra

Mr. Sachin S. Dethe

Research Scholar, Department of Commerce and Management,
Shivaji University, Kolhapur 416004

Corresponding author- Mr. Sachin S. Dethe

Email- sachin.dethe12@gmail.com

Abstract

Economic development is not only related to the production of goods and services but also developmental changes in all sectors of society. It is expected to convey the benefits of development to various sections of the society. Employment opportunities, reduction of poverty, reduction of economic disparity, raising the standard of living of all sections of the society, are called economic development. In the process of economic development, the concept of inclusive growth has come forward since the 11th plan so that the majority of the people in the rural and primary areas benefit not only a few people. The Social Justice and Tribal Department, which has been under constant discussion due to technical difficulties, office procrastination, insufficient manpower, various malpractices and diversion of funds, can achieve the goal of educational, social and economic upliftment of Scheduled Tribes, Nomadic Tribes, Tribals and other groups.

Key words: Social. Economic factors, government, development, community, backward class, disparity, reduction etc.

Introduction:

Various schemes are implemented by Social Justice Department in urban and rural areas. Personal benefit schemes include schemes such as pumps, cars, farm water lines, goat rearing, buffalo rearing, and fertilizers, activities for self-help groups, shelters, entrepreneurship promotion, inter-caste marriages, and land for the landless. In the education sector, various types of scholarships, stipends, tuition fees, hostels are arranged, for which thousands of crores of rupees are spent every year. The tribal department gets a fund of Rs.55000 crore every year. There are various plans, initiatives and programs on paper but their actual implementation is not effective. Even though cases of malpractices in scholarship, hostels and ashram schools have been happening for years, concrete measures have not been taken to check the personal benefit schemes of this department. Due to non-receipt of scholarship on time, inconvenience in hostels, incidents of injustice and oppression, students are taking out marches and agitations every year. There are schemes for Dalits, tribals; but due to oppressive conditions, lack of public awareness and corrupt system, the real beneficiaries remain deprived of these schemes. The Dadasaheb Gaikwad Empowerment Scheme for the landless was also not successful. Colleges themselves float scholarship funds in the name of bogus students, keeping tribals away from education due to this strange situation. Administration is certainly responsible for all these forms; but the difficulties of administration should also be understood.

Problems of the Study:

Scholarships worth crores have to be distributed by only three to four officers, the responsibility of other schemes is also on these

officers. Due to the fact that the latest technology is still not used sufficiently, there are difficulties in the work. The needy should be able to benefit from these schemes and achieve the goal of educational, social and economic upliftment of Scheduled Tribes, Nomadic Castes, Tribals and other sections. For that, implementation of schemes should be done in a transparent manner, strict criteria and their implementation should be emphasized. As the number of schemes is huge, it is not a situation where the officials can mention their names in one go. Consolidation of schemes, streamlining their functioning has been discussed for the last few years and should be accelerated. Evaluation of the work should be done after a certain period of time, so that it is convenient to remove the defects in time and convey them to the beneficiaries.

Objectives of the Study:

The main objective of this research is to study the benefit of the government schemes for the backward class people in Maharashtra and the problems faced during its actual implementation as well as the use of government schemes to solve the economic and social problems of the backward class people and the researcher has given some specific objectives as follows.

1. To Study the socio-economic condition of backward community.
2. To Study the implementation of government schemes for weaker sections.
3. To Study the factors affects Development of weaker sections.

Significance of the Study:

As we have welfare schemes for marginalized groups implemented by the government, similarly they are being implemented in other countries. There the marginalized are being

mainstreamed through the implementation of these schemes. What exactly are they doing for it? What is being done to ensure that the needy can really benefit from the scheme. The government and charitable organizations are jointly implementing various initiatives ranging from economic upliftment to technological development and skill development. From it, such elements are finding a new way to live. The opportunity to inform about such activities and meet such active congregations will come at the Delivering Change Forum conference to be held on January 24 and 25 at the Nehru Center in Mumbai. International level experts will guide and listen to the work experience of the marginalized.

Scope of the Study:

As the group develops, some elements fall behind. Although there are many reasons behind it, it is the responsibility of the government to achieve social justice by bringing them together with other social elements; but at the same time, this subject also needs broad social support. The deprived or weaker sections will not get justice unless the society accepts them, they also feel that they owe something to them. Therefore, it is the responsibility of all of us to create social convergence in this regard.

Period of the Study:

While studying the social and economic problems of the backward classes, the researcher has studied some of the factors in the year 2022-23 to study the benefits of the government schemes to the backward class people.

Limitation of the Study:

Individual benefit schemes and collective schemes are not implemented efficiently. Schemes for agriculture, employment, self-employment, skill development, education, student scholarship, land for agriculture, shelter, health are not implemented effectively. Changing this picture requires planning. Social and educational development of the concerned elements was expected to happen through this social justice department which is run according to the guidelines of the constitution. Even after sixty years, it has not achieved the expected success. A large amount of funds are provided by the central government to the state government for scholarships. But, no concerted efforts are made by the state government to deliver this fund to the concerned entity. Often this fund has been withdrawn. The plan to give land to the landless, started in the name of Dadasaheb Gaikwad, has also failed.

Research Methodology:

While studying the benefits of government schemes to the backward classes and the improvement in their economic and social conditions, researchers have used a number of secondary surveys. In this research paper, articles, journals, newspaper, audio video, reference books, serial books, government reports, magazines, etc., have been researched using descriptive method.

Research Method:

While reviewing the benefits of various schemes of the government to the backward classes and the change in the economic and social conditions of the backward class people, the researchers have completed the said research using the descriptive analysis method.

Results and Discussion:

Efforts are not made by the department to bring forward the schemes of caste eradication, inter-caste marriage etc. Such initiatives should be encouraged on the lines of Barti. Backward class, tribal society is living in adverse conditions. Efforts are needed to see how the schemes will reach every section of the society. In a welfare state, the marginalized, marginalized sections are always given a helping hand. But, here no work goes forward without intermediaries. The conditions in most schemes are impractical. Efforts should be made to reach the government schemes and funds to the grassroots level by using Anganwadis, women self-help groups.

Social Factors:

The number of students from different social groups is significant in urban and rural areas. Scholarships are also given by the central and state governments. But, the scholarship distribution system is not well organized. There is a need for the administration to streamline the distribution of caste certificates and scholarships by using the latest technology.

Government Schemes:

Some schemes are available only to political and administrative persons and their relatives. None of the schemes of the department reach the needy beneficiaries. As the vagabonds do not get certificates, they cannot avail the benefits of the government schemes. The department needs to create more awareness about these schemes in urban and rural areas. The proposal of Pardhi Rehabilitation Project has been pending with the government for many days. There is no separate financial provision for the development of this society and it also lags behind as the available funds are not utilized. In Solapur, the Pardhi community was surveyed and caste certificates were issued to them. Other locations were not surveyed. It is a fact that the stamp of crime on the society is still not erased.

Chart No. 1 Government Schemes and Development

Development and Backward class:

Various loan schemes are being implemented for the advancement of citizens belonging to other backward classes. Accordingly, a direct loan scheme of Rs. 25 thousand through the State Corporation for the concerned beneficiaries between the age of 18 to 50 years, 20 percent seed capital scheme as well as 45 percent margin money scheme of National Backward Classes Finance and Development Corporation in New Delhi, Swarnima scheme for women, term loan scheme, micro credit scheme, women prosperity scheme and educational loan scheme etc. are being implemented.

Decisions and Educational Development:

Along with the effective implementation of various schemes implemented for the economic, social and educational development of freed castes, nomadic tribes, other backward classes and special backward classes, the establishment of a new independent department for their overall development was approved in the meeting of the state cabinet on Tuesday. This department has been named as Unprivileged Castes, Nomadic Tribes, Other Backward Classes and Special Backward Classes Department. A period of three months has been given for the creation of the new department, and this department will be operational from April 1, 2017. Certain offices and corporations will be classified under this new administrative division. It includes the Directorate of Freed Caste-Nomadic Tribes, Other Backward Classes and Special Backward Classes in Pune; also includes Other Backward Classes Finance and Development Corporations and their offices and Vimukt Castes, Nomadic Tribes Development Corporations and their offices.

Factors effects on backward class:

On the basis of certain factors of backwardness such as illiteracy and lack of education, poverty, exploitation of labour, non-representation in services and untouchability, Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes are listed in the Constitution, while the third group i.e. Other Backward Classes is unlisted. On the basis of certain factors of backwardness such as illiteracy and educational poverty, exploitation of labour, lack of representation in services and untouchability, Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes are listed in the Constitution, while the third group i.e. Other Backward Classes is unlisted. Rather it is loosely defined.

Conclusion:

For the empowerment of socially and economically backward classes, other entities also have to take initiative. We can work together to create social interest more efficiently than the government. By making them employable and self-employed through education, training, the standard of living of these elements can be improved and raised. They can be comforted. Their developed models have been created by successfully conducting many such experiments abroad. Information about it will be heard from the famous people of international level along with their experience in this conference in Mumbai. Recognizing that Indian society is entirely poor, uneducated and composed of millions of citizens living in small, closed tribal and rural villages, the Constitution emphasizes social, economic and political justice with equity. Backward status is given on the basis of birth in some cases. Hence, for all practical purposes the term backward class is used for backward castes, while the Constitution recognizes special provisions for the advancement of any socially and economically backward class.

References:

1. B. R. Suryawanshi (2011), Role of MPBCDC in economic development of backward classes in Maharashtra with special reference to Nanded District, pp. 20-25.
2. Lokhande (2015), A study of socio-economic background of entrepreneurs from semi urban centers in Maharashtra, pp. 10-18.
3. Barman (2014), Socio-economic status of scheduled caste people in Kamrup District of Assam, pp. 1629-1640.
4. Kumar (2014), Socio-economic status of micro, small and medium enterprises in Himachal Pradesh: A case study of Hamirpur district, pp. 83-87.
5. Lokhande (2006), Entrepreneurship development among Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes in Marathwada Region, pp. 64-76.
6. Reddy (2003), Entrepreneurial process among scheduled castes and scheduled tribes in Andhra Pradesh, pp. 84.
7. Karunaratne (2001), Revisiting capital account convertibility in the aftermath of the Currency Crisis, pp. 264-271.